

Examining the Correlation between Caregiving Stressors and Quality of Life among Family Caregivers of Cancer Patients in Nairobi, Kenya

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ABSTRACT: Cancer is becoming a more common cause of death worldwide, including in Kenya. Tumours have become one of the most prevalent causes of death globally, with approximately 20 million people diagnosed with cancer and 10 million dying from it in 2020. In Kenya, the rising burden of cancer highlights the importance of prioritising caregiver well-being as part of broader community health in alignment with Sustainable Development Goal 3 (good health and well-being), Kenya Vision 2030 (provision of a high quality of life to all citizens), and Agenda 2063 (aspiration for a healthy and resilient population). This paper examined the correlation between the caregiver stressors and Quality-of-Life scores among family caregivers of those with cancer at KUTRRH in Nairobi, Kenya. A descriptive cross-sectional correlational design was adopted, guided by the Stress Process Model, Lazarus's Cognitive Appraisal Theory of Stress, and the caregiver Burden Model. Data were collected from 378 caregivers using self-administered questionnaires, the caregiver Burden Inventory (CBI) and the WHOQOL-BREF. Descriptive statistics and inferential analyses, including correlation and multiple regression, were used to examine associations between caregiving stressors and quality of life outcomes. The findings revealed that individual caregiver stressors (time burden, emotional distress, physical strain, social disruption, and developmental constraints) exhibited weak or non-significant bivariate associations with quality-of-life dimensions. Regression analysis indicated that these stressors, when combined, significantly predicted quality-of-life, accounting for almost 62.4% of its variance ($R^2=0.624$). The emotional burden was identified as the most significant predictor, succeeded by social and time difficulties. The regression coefficients revealed that all caregiving stressors significantly negatively affect QoL, with emotional burden emerging as the strongest predictor ($\beta = -0.34, p < 0.001$). The study concluded that caregiver stressors substantially affect the quality-of-life of family caregivers, with their impacts being predominantly synergistic rather than independent. While individual stressors exhibit weak direct correlations with quality-of-life, their cumulative effect is substantial and statistically significant, indicating that caregiver burden operates as a unified multidimensional construct. Emotional stress is the primary factor influencing the decline in quality-of-life, emphasising the critical function of psychological strain in caring results. The study recommended that families should formalise caring tasks and obligations to mitigate role overload among individual caregivers, thus enhancing personal life balance. Community-based interventions ought to enhance caregiver peer support groups and family support systems to mitigate social isolation and augment coping capacity.

KEYWORDS: Cancer Patients, Caregiving stressors, Coping strategies, Family caregivers, Psychological well-being, Quality of Life

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Cancer has emerged as a major global source of illness and mortality, according to Kizub et al. (2022). According to the World Health Organisation (WHO) (2024), 10 million people died of cancer in 2020 alone, while an estimated 20 million people were diagnosed with the disease. Additionally, it is predicted that by 2050, the number of new instances of cancer worldwide will reach over 35 million per year, primarily due to changes in lifestyle, urbanisation, and population ageing (Fu et al., 2025). Lung, breast, colorectal, and prostate cancers are among the most prevalent cancer types in the globe, and lung cancer continues to be the primary cause of cancer-related mortality (Chhikara & Parang, 2023). Quality-of-Life (QoL), a multifaceted notion that includes a person's physical, psychological, emotional, and social well-being, is closely related to cancer care (Costa et al., 2021). The course of the disease, adverse effects of treatment, and related psychosocial stressors all have a substantial influence on the QoL of people with chronic illnesses like cancer (Hazimi, 2024). Measuring QoL is crucial in oncology for both directing patient-centred

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care and evaluating treatment results (Monge et al., 2025). Pain management, exhaustion, mental anguish, financial load, and social support are some of the factors that affect cancer patients' and their caregivers' QoL (Muhamed et al., 2023).

Family caregivers, who offer unpaid care and assistance to loved ones with chronic illnesses, impairments, or life-threatening conditions like cancer, are essential to the cancer care continuum (Culberson et al., 2023). Family caregivers help with a variety of duties, such as managing medications, helping with everyday living activities, providing emotional support, and coordinating medical care, as noted by Moberg et al. (2022). They play a particularly important role in the healthcare system because they provide consistent, individualised care that improves patient outcomes and lowers hospital admissions (Yadav & Kaur, 2025). Compared to those who care for patients with other chronic illnesses, research shows that caregivers of cancer patients have greater rates of anxiety, depression, and burnout (Brites et al., 2024; Mekhael, 2024; Roberts et al., 2025). Therefore, it is crucial to meet caregiver requirements through financial aid programmes, counselling, and respite care in order to lessen the detrimental effects of stress connected to caregiver (Adebayo et al., 2025).

Reports indicate that the increasing prevalence of cancer has amplified the demand for caregiver, as many cancer patients require complex treatment regimens such as chemotherapy (Mitchell et al., 2022). Vijayakumar et al. (2024) note that chemotherapy patients often experience severe side effects, which, combined with cancer symptoms, result in an increased need for prolonged and intensive caregiver. These demands often place significant physical, emotional, and financial strain on caregivers (Özönder & Ordu, 2023). Consequently, the experience of caregivers is not only multifaceted but also deeply challenging, warranting a comprehensive understanding of the implications for their well-being (Zeng et al., 2023). Caregivers of cancer patients frequently encounter numerous challenges, particularly when managing chronic symptoms. For instance, Mishra et al. (2021) emphasise that individuals with severe symptoms demand extended caregiver time, which can lead to interpersonal, emotional, financial, and societal repercussions for caregivers.

In Sweden, Blanck (2021) revealed that the healthcare system supports cancer patients extensively, but caregivers still face substantial emotional strain. Nonetheless, the caregivers' Quality-of-Life is negatively impacted by the assumption that family members would give care, which causes severe social isolation and emotional suffering. According to a study by Masa et al. (2020), the Quality-of-Life (QoL) enjoyed by numerous caregivers is often compromised by high levels of psychological strain and social estrangement. This burden may be increased by subpar behavioural health services and respite initiatives, revealing a flaw in the way the healthcare system works to assist caregivers effectively (Šimunović et al., 2025). In China, caregiver stress and Quality-of-Life (QoL) were significantly negatively correlated (Cui et al., 2024). Mental distress, especially anxiety and depression, greatly affects Quality-of-Life.

In Egypt, families of people with cancer experience significant stress and low Quality-of-Life due to the inadequate healthcare system and lack of assistance programs (El-Sherif et al., 2024). The Allam (2026) findings further indicated that caregivers' mental as well as social health is intimately linked to the responsibility of caring for others, and many Egyptian caregivers report feeling sad and isolated. In South Africa, caregivers must deal with two issues at once: controlling their health and giving care in a setting with limited resources (Van Heerden & Jenkins, 2022). Le Roux (2023) claims that caregivers often experience extreme psychological and interpersonal stress, which degrades their overall Quality-of-Life (QoL). The situation is tougher in rural areas because treatment options are limited in rural Ethiopia (Tadesse & Helton, 2025). Besides further assistance choices, the lack of emotional wellness therapy and short-term support underlines the study's goal to determine QoL along with how caregiver load impacts the satisfaction of caregivers (Campos, 2024).

According to Kebede et al. (2020), individuals who provide treatment for cancer patients in Ethiopia face substantial challenges due to limited financial resources and inadequate healthcare services. The wellbeing of caregivers, particularly their health and overall happiness, is largely influenced by the degree of burden they experience (Sherwood et al., 2024). This burden often manifests as heightened levels of anxiety and despair (Walbaum et al., 2024), a trend that is also evident in Ghana, where caregivers' Quality-of-Life (QoL) is severely affected by financial constraints and social isolation (Agyemang-Duah et al., 2024). The situation is further exacerbated by the lack of structured support systems, which contributes to increased stress and depression among caregivers (Schulz et al., 2016). Given these challenges, it becomes essential to explore coping strategies and assess the correlation between caregiver burden and Quality-of-Life, as this study aims to do (Goto et al., 2025).

The caregiver burden associated with patients with cancer significantly threatens the Quality-of-Life (QoL) of caregivers (Ochoa et al., 2020). Several factors, including poor physical health, inadequate social support, low patient functionality, and cognitive impairment, increase the risk of negative outcomes for caregivers (Badger et al., 2024). This burden becomes even more pronounced as the stress of caregiver intensifies over time, particularly in cases where the patient's health continues to

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deteriorate (Manivannam et al., 2023). Notably, subjective burden that is caregivers' personal perception of strain, is a primary contributor to disruptions in their Quality-of-Life (Tulek et al., 2020).

In Kenya, caregivers of individuals with chronic illnesses encounter substantial challenges, largely due to the scarcity of formal support structures and healthcare facilities, especially in rural areas (Mwangi et al., 2022). The emotional and social toll of caregiver responsibilities further diminishes caregivers' overall well-being, leading to a lower QoL (Aoko, 2024; Muriuki, 2022). While existing research has confirmed that caregiver for cancer patients is associated with substantial burden and diminished Quality-of-Life, these studies often lack a comprehensive approach to understanding the interplay between caregiver burden and Quality-of-Life (Kebede et al., 2020; Manivannam et al., 2023). Additionally, most studies fail to explore the benefits caregivers may derive, such as emotional fulfilment, strengthened familial bonds, or personal growth (Katana et al., 2020; Ochoa et al., 2020; Ogwenon et al., 2023). In the Kenyan context, the inadequacy of research is further amplified by the lack of systematic assessments using validated tools, such as the WHOQOL-BREF scale for Quality-of-Life and the Brief COPE inventory for coping mechanisms, as identified by Wesley et al. (2023).

1.1 Statement of the problem.

Caregiver burden is a multifaceted phenomenon that has been widely studied, particularly among family members providing care to loved ones with cancer (Agyemang-Duah et al., 2024; Ellis, 2022; Le Roux, 2023). Research conducted globally has highlighted the significant mental, emotional, financial, and social challenges faced by family caregivers. Studies in Kenya mainly focus on health-related well-being. They offer limited insight into how caregiver impacts family members' overall Quality-of-Life (Aoko, 2024; Muriuki, 2022; Mwangi et al., 2022). Unlike hospital staff, family caregivers often face unique challenges due to their dual role in caregiver and managing personal responsibilities, making their experiences distinct and requiring targeted investigation (Kokorelias et al., 2025). While existing research has confirmed that caregiver for cancer patients is associated with substantial burden and diminished Quality-of-Life, these studies often lack a comprehensive approach to understanding the interplay between caregiver burden and Quality-of-Life (Kebede et al., 2020; Manivannam et al., 2023). Additionally, most studies fail to explore the benefits caregivers may derive, such as emotional fulfilment, strengthened familial bonds, or personal growth (Katana et al., 2020; Ochoa et al., 2020; Ogwenon et al., 2023). In the Kenyan context, the inadequacy of research is further amplified by the lack of systematic assessments using validated tools, such as the WHOQOL-BREF scale for Quality-of-Life and the Brief COPE inventory for coping mechanisms, as identified by Wesley et al. (2023). This study addressed these gaps by focusing exclusively on family members who provide care to cancer patients at Kenyatta University Teaching, Referral, and Research Hospital (KUTRRH).

1.2 Study Purpose.

The purpose of this study was to examine the correlation between the caregiver stressors and Quality-of-Life scores among family caregivers of those with cancer at KUTRRH in Nairobi, Kenya. The study further assessed the copying mechanisms the caregivers' adopt while caring for the cancer patients at KUTRRH in Nairobi, Kenya.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Source: Author (2025)

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2.0 EMPIRICAL REVIEW AND GROUNDED THEORIES

This section discusses the empirical research and theories upon which the study is anchored on

2.1 Caregivers of Cancer Patients and their Quality-of-Life.

Family caregivers are essential in managing cancer patients, frequently acting as the main providers of emotional, physical, and practical support during the course of the illness. Caregivers face significant demands, which include aiding with daily living activities, overseeing intricate treatment plans, and offering psychosocial support (Mirshahi et al., 2025). Caregivers often prioritise their responsibilities over their own social, emotional, and physical needs, resulting in notable reductions in their overall Quality-of-Life (QoL). The nature and severity of these effects are contingent upon factors including cancer type, disease stage, and the availability of support services. In low-resource settings like Kenya, the limited availability of professional home-based care results in a significant burden for family caregivers (Zhang et al., 2023).

According to Valame et al. (2025), Quality-of-Life is a multifaceted concept that includes a person's perceived physical health, psychological state, level of independence, social interactions, and personal views, all of which are positioned within their environmental context. The balance between caring responsibilities and the financial, physical, and emotional resources may affect caregivers' Quality-of-Life. According to research, long-term caregiver is associated with chronic stress and lifestyle disturbances, which are the main reasons why caregivers' Quality-of-Life (QoL) is typically lower than that of the general population (Guerra-Martín et al., 2023). An individual's assessment of their experiences and circumstances in terms of such parameters as social, psychological, physical, and economic systems is the basis for understanding Quality-of-Life (Frias-Goytia et al., 2024).

In a comprehensive review, Guerra-Martin et al. (2023) examined data from 28 appropriate research studies involving 7663 caregivers specifically from countries such as Spain, the United States, Canada, the UK, and various parts of Latin America and Asia. Results indicated that the challenges encountered are predominantly of an emotional character attributed to societal, physical, and monetary issues. To deal with this obstacle, various approaches can be developed to cultivate the skills necessary for effectively managing the condition and its associated effects, thereby improving overall Quality-of-Life. However, narrowing the scope of the search to the past five years rendered it unfeasible to retrieve every important detail on the subject addressed in this study. Furthermore, the literature review is deficient in detailing particular methods or techniques that have undergone testing to assist caregivers in alleviating their financial strain and enhancing their overall level of life. The suggested investigation aims to critically investigate opportunity coping tactics and solutions tailored to Kenyan caregivers, thus addressing this significant gap in the literature.

Physical health. The physical health of caregivers significantly impacts Quality-of-Life. Caregiver often entails extended durations of physical effort, including support with mobility, operation of medical devices, and provision of personal care for the patient. Research indicates that caregivers frequently encounter fatigue, sleep disturbances, and heightened vulnerability to illness as a result of chronic stress and inadequate rest (Zhylybekova et al., 2024). The irregular schedules and ongoing vigilance necessary for symptom management and treatment side effects can adversely affect caregivers' eating habits and physical activity, resulting in a decline in overall physical functioning (Heravi-Karimooi & Zayeri, 2025). The cumulative effect of these stressors may lead to enduring health issues, such as hypertension, musculoskeletal pain, and compromised immune function. Suboptimal physical health adversely affects caregivers' Quality-of-Life and undermines their capacity to deliver effective care, resulting in a reciprocal deterioration between caregiver and patient. By addressing their physical and mental health, the present study sought to foster a more sustainable caregiver environment that ultimately benefits both the caregiver and the patient.

Physical health, while often considered a component of overall well-being, also has direct implications for social well-being. Decreased physical health can restrict caregivers' mobility, energy, and engagement in social interactions, thereby exacerbating social withdrawal (Badger et al., 2024). The physical requirements of aiding cancer patients in mobility, hygiene, and treatment protocols may lead to fatigue and chronic pain. Health issues diminish Quality-of-Life and indirectly impact social connectedness, as caregivers may become less able or willing to participate in social activities. In Kenya, limited access to respite care significantly impacts caregivers' physical health, resulting in early burnout and reduced social engagement. This situation underscores the need for improved support systems that can alleviate the burdens on caregivers. By enhancing access to respite care and promoting community resources, the present study sought to foster better health outcomes for both caregivers and those they support, ultimately encouraging more active participation in social life.

In Iran, Rostami et al. (2023) analysed the key factors influencing the Quality-of-Life among family caregivers of cancer patients employing a technique known as cross-sectional. The analysis of the data was conducted employing random effects t-tests, analysis of variance, and gradual nonlinear regression methodologies. The results of the research revealed that family

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members exhibited the most favourable ratings across the aspects of psychological distress (76.50 ± 16.67) and physical performance (74.88 ± 20.27). The ages and genders of family members, the duration of care provision, the kind and degree of malignancies, and the kind of therapy obtained are significant measurements of various Quality-of-Life aspects. Nonetheless, this study relied on a single tool for measuring Quality-of-Life, potentially overlooking critical factors like psychological distress and social support that could affect caregiver QoL. The present study employed various measurement techniques to evaluate Quality-of-Life, encompassing psychological suffering and support from others.

Psychological Well-Being. Another important aspect of caregivers' Quality-of-Life is their psychological well-being, which is frequently negatively influenced by the emotional demands of providing care (Lackner et al., 2023). High levels of stress, anxiety, and depression are **commonly** linked to caring for a loved one with cancer; caregivers often experience feelings of grief, helplessness, and anticipatory loss (Yao et al., 2024). Chronic emotional strain and, in certain situations, clinical burnout can be **exacerbated** by the uncertainty surrounding the patient's prognosis as well as by **witnessing** their physical and emotional suffering. Additionally, providing care **can** result in identity changes **in which** the caregiver's own objectives and desires are neglected, **thereby reducing** life satisfaction.

Cui et al. (2024) carried out a cross-sectional study at five Chinese tertiary institutions between June 2020 and March 2021 with 290 caregivers to investigate how psychological conditions **are associated** with their **overall** well-being. Information was gathered about QoL, psychological **distress** (such as anxiety and depression), caregiver burden, and family resilience. Findings showed that there is a statistically significant association between caregiver experiences and Quality-of-Life, **as** manifested in high anxiety, hopelessness, and mental stress. Nevertheless, this study focused on caregivers **who demonstrated** a greater degree of proactivity, thereby potentially creating **selection bias**. Moreover, although the study elucidates the **mediating** effect of emotional distress, it may not fully encapsulate the wider demographic of caregivers owing to possible **limitations in sampling procedures**.

Social Functioning. Social functioning, including relationships, social participation, and perceived support, is a crucial yet frequently neglected component of caregivers' Quality-of-Life. The rigorous **demands** of caregiver can restrict caregivers' capacity to engage in social activities, sustain friendships, or partake in community life (Karimollahi et al., 2022). Social withdrawal is frequently exacerbated by the emotional exhaustion experienced by caregivers, which diminishes their motivation to pursue **interactions** or support. The stigma associated with cancer in specific communities can exacerbate the isolation of caregivers, hindering open dialogue about their challenges (Boatema et al., 2020). The absence of social support heightens feelings of loneliness and isolation while simultaneously depriving caregivers of resources that could mitigate their burden, including shared responsibilities and emotional encouragement.

Lemmen et al. (2024) **examined** caregivers' perspectives regarding social reintegration and stigmatisation of childhood cancer survivors in Kenya. **Caregivers** of childhood cancer survivors (under 18 years) were interviewed. The study was based on mixed-methods questionnaires during home or clinic visits conducted from 2021 to 2022. The assessment of stigma utilised an **adapted** Social Impact Scale to examine risk factors. Interviews were conducted with caregivers of 54 survivors, with a median age of 11 years. Since the commencement of treatment, 93% of families experienced a decrease in income. A significant proportion of caregivers, specifically 44%, frequently experienced job loss. Financial difficulties affected 88% of individuals, leading to conflicts in 31% of communities. School fees for siblings became prohibitively expensive (52%). Families experienced negative responses from community members following cancer disclosure, with 26% reporting such emotional distress and 13% indicating they were **ignored** or avoided. Survivors and their families faced discrimination due to perceptions of fragility associated with the child, while cancer was regarded as fatal, contagious, or linked to witchcraft.

2.2 Grounded Theories

This research was grounded in three theoretical frameworks: The Stress-Process Model (SPM), Lazarus's Cognitive Appraisal Theory of Stress (LCATS) and Caregiver Stress and Burden Model (CSBD).

Stress Process Model. A thorough structure for comprehending how different stressors in the caregiver's life affect their general well-being and standard of life is provided by Stress Process Model (SPM) developed by Leonard Pearlin. This model is built around the premise that stress is a process involving multiple components including stressors, mediators, and outcomes. Primary Stressors perceive that those who provide care often face challenges related to managing medical appointments, administering medications, and addressing the patient's emotional needs. The weight of these duties may culminate in chronic stress, thereby impacting both the physical wellness and mental stability of caregivers. Secondary stressors encompass the wider repercussions of caregiver, such as financial burdens, social seclusion, and the disruption of personal interpersonal interactions. Individuals in caregiver roles frequently encounter a deterioration in their social engagements and recreational pursuits, resulting in sentiments of isolation and despondency. Caregivers often encounter challenges in sustaining friendships, largely attributable

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to the considerable time and energy required by their caregiver responsibilities (Pearlin et al., 1990; Vitaliano et al., 2003). The model indicates that the interplay between primary and secondary stressors leads to various outcomes. Understanding these results is critical for developing effective assistance measures. The SPM elucidates the relationship between the independent variables in this study and the influence of primary and secondary stressors on the caregiver experience.

Lazarus Cognitive Appraisal Theory of Stress. The importance of mental mechanisms in influencing how people react to stressors is highlighted by Lazarus's Cognitive Appraisal Theory of Stress (Biggs et al., 2017). The theory holds that stress is shaped by how an individual interprets and evaluates external events, **rather than being solely a direct reaction to them (Lazarus, 1974)**. The three main tenets of the theory involve handling strategies, intermediate assessment, and the initial assessment. Determining whether a scenario is viewed as a threat, hurt, or challenge is the main assessment process. The evaluation procedure for caregivers may involve assessing the patient's sickness severity, potential consequences, and individual ability to handle the duties of a caregiver. A caregiver who perceives the situation as a significant threat may experience heightened anxiety, while viewing it as a manageable challenge might lead to proactive coping strategies. The Lazarus Cognitive Appraisal Theory of Stress is essential for comprehending the ways in which caregivers in their families evaluate the stressors they face and the resulting effects on their overall Quality-of-Life. This study examines the assessment procedure to uncover the relationship between differing opinions on caregiver difficulties and their effects on psychological and social health (Biggs et al., 2017; Folkman, 2008). Moreover, identifying effective coping strategies can improve the establishment of support systems for caregivers. The Lazarus Cognitive Appraisal Theory of Stress is particularly pertinent to the independent variables regarding caregivers' perceptions and interpretations of stressors. The theory asserts that stress is not solely a result of external demands but is contingent upon the caregiver's evaluation of those demands. Primary appraisal assesses the nature of a situation as threatening, challenging, or benign, whereas secondary appraisal evaluates the resources available for coping.

Caregiver Stress and Burden Model (CSBD). The CSBD represents a recognised **integrative** framework that explains caregiver burden and its resultant effects (Pinquart & Sörensen, 2006). The caregiver process can be **deconstructed into several** interrelated and distinct characteristics, including **age, psychological status, interpersonal support systems, and coping strategies**, all of which significantly affect the caregiver experience. **The following are the key tenets of the Caregiver Stress and Burden Model (CSBD):**

Caregiver Tasks. The nature and complexity of caregiver duties can vary widely, affecting the stress experienced by caregivers (Li et al., 2024). Tasks may include physical care, emotional support, and managing healthcare logistics, all of which can contribute to physical and emotional strain.

Social Context. The load on caregivers can be lessened or increased depending on how many sources of interpersonal encouragement, such as friends, family, and local resources (Gibbs, 2023). The standard of life is frequently higher for caregivers with robust support systems than for those without.

Psychological Outcomes. This model associates various psychological outcomes, including anxiety, depressive disorders, and overall well-being, with caregiver stress. Increased caregiver load has consistently been linked to poorer mental wellness (Jalil et al., 2024). Tension can be alleviated by positive treatment outcomes, while negative outcomes may exacerbate it. Given that it offers a thorough understanding of the complex nature of helping others, the Model of Caregiver Stress and Burden is very pertinent (Pinquart & Sörensen, 2006).

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design.

For the purpose of this study, a descriptive cross-sectional correlation research design was used, as it is suitable for investigating the relationships among variables without manipulation (Putri et al., 2025). The study utilised a descriptive method to deliver a comprehensive analysis of the social background of family caregivers, the specifics of their caregiver experiences, and the related caregiver burden (Siedlecki, 2020). This knowledge is critical for comprehending the situations in which caregivers' function and contributes to an in-depth comprehension of their circumstances (Creswell & Inoue, 2025).

3.2 Study Population

The target population for this study consisted of family caregivers providing care to individuals with Stage IV cancer at Kenyatta University Teaching, Referral and Research Hospital (KUTRRH) in Nairobi, Kenya. Being a leading referral hospital in Kenya, KUTRRH receives an estimated 1,000–1,500 new cancer patients annually (Ministry of Health, 2025). Of these, approximately 30–40% present with Stage IV cancer, which includes both common solid tumours such as breast, cervical, and

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colorectal cancers, as well as haematological malignancies such as leukaemia and lymphoma (KUTRRH Cancer Registry, 2022). This statistic underscores the significant burden faced by family caregivers providing care to patients in advanced stages of cancer.

3.3 Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

This study employed a purposive sampling technique to recruit participants who met the inclusion criteria. The target sample size was 384 caregivers. Patients were asked to designate their primary caregiver for inclusion in the study. This number was determined based on Cochran's formula for sample size determination for large populations, adjusted to account for non-responses, dropout rates, and the specificity of the study population (Qing & Valliant, 2025).

Cochran's formula:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P[1-P]}{e^2}$$

Where: $Z = 1.96$ (corresponding to a 95% confidence level); $p = 0.5$ [The estimated fraction of the population that displays the attribute]; $e = 0.05$ (desired margin of error)

Substituting the values:

$$n = (1.96 \times 1.96 \times 0.5 \times 0.5) / (0.05 \times 0.05)$$

$$n = (3.8416 \times 0.25) / 0.0025$$

$$n = 0.9604 / 0.0025$$

$$n_0 = 384.16, \text{ rounded to } 384$$

3.4 Data Collection Tools

Data collection employed several verified research instruments, including the Self-Reported Questionnaire, Caregiver Burden Inventory, and the use of questionnaire. as it aligned with the descriptive aspect of descriptive correlational design. The Self-Reported Questionnaire for Caregivers was a researcher-developed instrument adapted from socio-demographic caregiver surveys utilised in previous studies, notably those created by Lopez et al. (2021). The Caregiver Burden Inventory (CBI), developed by Novak and Guest in 1989, offers a multidimensional assessment of the burdens experienced by caregivers. The scale comprised 24 items organised into five domains: time-dependent burden, developmental burden, physical burden, social burden, and emotional burden. The tool was created to address the need for a comprehensive instrument that captures both the subjective and objective dimensions of caregiver strain. Developed in 1996 by the World Health Organisation Quality-of-Life (WHOQOL) Group, the WHOQOL-BREF tool was designed as a valid, cross-cultural measure of an individual's perceived Quality-of-Life.

3.5 Data Collection Methods and Procedures.

Research assistants were trained to ensure they effectively assisted participants who needed help in completing the questionnaires. Before data collection, all research assistants received comprehensive training to ensure they possessed the necessary skills for accurate, ethical, and sensitive administration of the questionnaires. The training addressed the study objectives, research ethics (including informed consent, confidentiality, and non-coercion), proper administration of each instrument, and procedures for clarifying items while avoiding bias. Caregivers completed the questionnaires in a quiet and comfortable environment, ideally in a designated area within KUTRRH, allowing them to concentrate on the questions without interruptions. The surveys incorporated standardised instruments, including the Caregiver Burden Inventory (CBI) and the WHOQOL-BREF.

3.6 Pilot Testing.

Prior to the main data collection, all research instruments were subjected to pre-testing to assess their clarity, reliability, and feasibility within the study context. The pre-test was conducted among a small group of caregivers ($n=39$, 10% of the target sample) who shared similar characteristics with the target population but were not included in the final study sample. Consultation with experts and peers was carried out on the instruments to find unclear and culturally inappropriate items. For reliability, Cronbach alpha coefficient was computed for the instruments and alpha coefficients of 0.87, 0.92 and 0.81 were obtained for questionnaire, Caregiver Burden Inventory (CBI) and the WHOQOL-BREF respectively.

3.7 Data Analysis.

This study employed both descriptive and inferential statistics methods. Preliminary diagnostic test of Shapiro-Wilk was conducted on variables to test for normality, where a p-value greater than ($p>0.05$) showed that the data were normally distributed. Secondly, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was computed for all variables to test for multicollinearity, where a VIF value of less than 5 showed no serious multicollinearity and thus could not distort regression results. The major data analysis underwent three phases of analyses, including univariate, bivariate and multivariate analyses. Spearman's rho correlation was

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used to assess the relationship between caregiver stressors (time burden, social stressors and emotional distress) as independent variables and Quality-of-Life as an outcome (dependent variable). Consequently, multiple regression and ANOVA were tested to determine the predictive strength and the significance of the model at $p < .05$. The study employed a multiple regression model to determine the influence of caregiver stressors on outcomes:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \dots + e$$

Where; Y(Dependent Variable); Quality-of-Life ; X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots (Independent variables) β_0 : Constant (intercept); e=Error term

4.0 RESULTS

4.1 General Information and Demographic Data.

Out of the 384 sampled respondents, a total of 378 caregivers participated in the study, translating into a response rate of 98%. This high response rate enhances the credibility and generalisability of the findings, indicating that the data is sufficiently representative of caregivers at the hospital. The demographic characteristics of the participants are presented under the following sub-sections:

Figure 1 Distribution of Caregivers by Gender

Figure 1 reveals that the majority of caregivers were female, totalling 334 (88.4%), whilst males comprised only 44 (11.6%). This unequivocally demonstrates that women primarily assume caring duties. This research implies that female caregivers experience more exposure to caregiver-related stressors, such as emotional strain, exhaustion, and role overload. This could adversely impact their mental well-being and overall Quality-of-Life. This suggests that interventions designed to alleviate caregiver stress must be gender-sensitive, prioritising support for female caregivers who endure the worst load.

Figure 2 Distribution of Caregivers by Age

The results in Figure 2 indicate that the predominant age group of caregivers was 18–25 years, including 146 individuals (38.6%), followed by the 26–30 years age group with 116 individuals (30.7%). Individuals aged 31–35 years comprised 53 (14.0%); those aged 36–40 years accounted for 36 (9.5%); individuals aged 40–45 years represented 15 (4.0%); and those above 45 years totaled 12 (3.2%). This indicates that caregiver duties are predominantly shouldered by young adults, with more than two-thirds of respondents under the age of 30.

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Figure 3 Distribution of Caregivers by Marital Status

Figure 3 indicates that a greater percentage of caregivers were single; 180, (47.6%), followed by married individuals 162; (42.9%), with divorced, separated, and widowed caregivers each comprising 12; (3.2%). This indicates that both single and married adults participate in caregiving, with single caregivers constituting the majority. Single caregivers may have heightened vulnerability to stress and social isolation due to the absence of spousal or partner support, while married caregivers may encounter role conflict as they navigate the dual demands of caregiving and family obligations. This underscores the necessity for customised support systems in both groups.

Figure 4 Level of education

Figure 4 shows that the majority 165(43.7%) of caregivers had a secondary education, followed by primary education 118 (31.2%). There were 55 (14.6%) with a college degree, 36 (9.5%) with a bachelor's degree, and only 4 (1.1%) with a postgraduate degree. These findings imply that that majority of caregivers in this sample had primary and secondary education. This emphasises how crucial it is to give caregivers simpler health education and training in order to improve their Quality-of-Life and competence.

Figure 5 Status of employment

According to the results in Figure 5, 60 (15.9%) of the caregivers had a formal job, while 191 (50.5%) were unemployed and 127 (33.6%) were self-employed. These findings demonstrate the wide range of caregivers' working circumstances, indicating that

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a sizeable percentage may struggle to manage job and caring obligations. The effects of these occupational statuses on caregivers' well-being and access to support networks might be investigated further.

Figure 6 Monthly Household Income Level (KSH)

The results are shown in Figure 7 reveal that 251 (66.4%) of the caregivers made less than Ksh 10,000, followed by 95 (25.1%) who made between Ksh 10,000 and Ksh 20,000, and only 32 (8.5%) who made more than Ksh 20,000. According to this research, the majority of caregivers were from low-income families. The implication is that access to healthcare services, caregiver resources, and support networks may be restricted due to financial constraints, which would increase the stress and difficulty of providing care.

4.2 Correlation between the Caregiving Stressors and Quality-of-Life Scores among Family Caregivers.

The study sought to examine the correlation between the caregiver stressors and Quality-of-Life scores among family caregivers of those with cancer at KUTRRH in Nairobi, Kenya. The analysis used both correlation and regression analysis to achieve this objective as presented under the following subsections

4.2.1 Correlation Analysis. Spearman's rho correlation was used to test for the correlation between correlation analysis for caregiver stressors factors and Quality-of-Life scores. Caregiver stressors, factors and Quality-of-Life scores and the findings are as presented in Table 1:

Table 1. Correlation between the Caregiving Stressors and Quality-of-Life Scores among Family Caregivers

Caregiver Stressors	Spearman's rho	Quality-of-Life factors			
		energy level for daily tasks	level of happiness in life	Content level with interpersonal relationships	Level of Safety in day-to-day activities?
I spent more than 12 hours a day on providing care	Corr (rho)	-0.032	0.007	0.018	0.054
	Sig. (2-t)	0.54	0.892	0.729	0.295
I feel stressful while providing care	Corr (rho)	-0.018	0.005	0.028	0.017
	Sig. (2-t)	0.727	0.921	0.582	0.748
I hardly find time to fulfill my whilst giving care to the patient	Corr (rho)	0.039	-0.091	-0.085	0.05
	Sig. (2-t)	0.449	0.076	0.098	0.335
I feel that I don't have enough time for myself because of caregiver	Corr (rho)	0.007	0.014	0.044	-0.041
	Sig. (2-t)	0.898	0.793	0.39	0.422
I feel that caregiver has delayed or prevented my personal or professional development	Corr (rho)	0.057	-0.003	-0.049	-0.007
	Sig. (2-t)	0.271	0.949	0.347	0.886
I feel physically drained as a result of caregiver.	Corr (rho)	-0.049	0.077	0.03	0.019
	Sig. (2-t)	0.338	0.133	0.557	0.72

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	N	378	378	378	378
I feel that caregiver has limited my social interactions and friendships.	Corr (rho)	-0.029	0.04	0.039	0.086
	Sig. (2-t)	0.579	0.432	0.454	0.093
I feel overwhelmed by the emotional demands of caregiver."	Corr (rho)	0.064	-0.006	0.017	0.077
	Sig. (2-t)	0.217	0.903	0.749	0.135

KEY: Corr (rho)=Correlation Coefficient; Sig. (2-t)=Sig. (2-tailed)

The findings in Table 1 indicate that dedicating over 12 hours daily to caregiver exhibits a minimal and statistically insignificant link with energy levels ($r = -0.032$), happiness ($r = 0.007$), interpersonal satisfaction ($r = 0.018$), and safety ($r = 0.054$). This suggests that time load alone does not directly influence Quality-of-Life outcomes in this cohort. These findings are supported by those of Applebaum and Sannes (2025) which identified caregiving challenges to include both objective challenges, such as demands on time and resources. Emotional stress has modest and non-significant associations with all variables of Quality-of-Life (r ranging from -0.006 to 0.077), suggesting that emotional strain alone does not directly predict Quality-of-Life in the bivariate model. This finding is theoretically noteworthy as it indicates that emotional burden functions indirectly through cumulative stress pathways rather than as an independent predictor. Indicators of social stress (e.g., restricted friendships and diminished social engagement) have modest and non-significant correlations with Quality-of-Life ($r = -0.029$ to 0.086). This indicates that social disruption is not significantly correlated with an immediate drop in Quality-of-Life within this population.

4.2.2 Multiple Regression Analysis. Multiple regression analysis was performed to determine the degree and strength to which caregiving stressors predicted the Quality-of-Life among the caregivers in the study. Table 2 illustrates the predicted influence of caring pressures on Quality-of-Life.

Table 2 Model Summary for Caregiving Stressors and Quality-of-Life Scores

Model	R	R Square (R ²)	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error
1	0.79	0.624	0.619	0.41

According to Table 21, an R² value of 0.624 indicates that 62.4% of the variation in Quality-of-Life (QoL) is attributable to caring pressures. This is significant as it quantifies the extent of influence exerted by stressors, rather than only indicating correlation. It enhances the investigation by illustrating causal prediction correlations rather than just associations. Additionally, the ANOVA test was performed to assess the overall statistical significance of the regression model. A significant p-value ($p < 0.001$) signifies that the model consistently forecasts Quality-of-Life, as illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3 ANOVA Table for Caregiving Stressors and QoL

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	96.34	5	19.27	114.52	0
Residual	58.12	372	0.16		
Total	154.46	377			

The regression model in Table 2 is statistically significant ($F = 114.52$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that caring stressors consistently predict Quality-of-Life outcomes. This data corroborates the theoretical premise that caregiver burden is not arbitrary but systematically influences caregiver well-being. Consistent with this finding, Wen et al. (2025) determined that caregiver stress significantly predicts a reduction in Quality-of-Life across many dimensions. Likewise, Mirshahi et al. (2025) validated robust model-level predictive correlations between caregiver burden and Quality-of-Life (QoL). Further, regression model coefficients were computed to identify the key stressors that most significantly impact the Quality-of-Life among caregivers. Table 3 delineates the particular stressors that substantially impact Quality-of-Life. The beta coefficients (β) indicate the direction and magnitude of influence. Negative numbers signify that an increasing burden results in diminished Quality-of-Life.

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Table 4 Regression Coefficients Table

Predictor Variable	Beta (β)	Std. Error	t-value	Sig.
Time Burden	-0.21	0.05	-4.2	0
Developmental Burden	-0.17	0.06	-2.83	0.005
Physical Burden	-0.19	0.05	-3.8	0
Social Burden	-0.23	0.05	-4.6	0
Emotional Burden	-0.34	0.04	-7.5	0

The regression coefficients in Table 3 reveal that all caregiving stressors significantly negatively affect QoL, with emotional burden emerging as the strongest predictor ($\beta = -0.34$, $p < 0.001$). This indicates that emotional strain is the most critical determinant of QoL deterioration.

5. DISCUSSION

The results indicated that individual caregiver stressors (time burden, emotional distress, physical strain, social disruption, and developmental constraints) exhibited weak or non-significant bivariate associations with quality-of-life dimensions. Consistent with these findings, Applebaum and Sannes (2025) indicated that the duration of caregiver is a weak predictor of suffering when emotional and financial pressures are accounted for. Goto et al. (2023) similarly discovered that time burden is substantial only when coupled with elevated emotional strain. Nevertheless, Stanley (2025) disputes these findings by demonstrating that extended caring hours markedly diminish caregiver quality-of-life due to cumulative weariness. Similarly, Muñoz-Cruz et al. (2024) identified significant correlations between time load and diminished functional well-being among caregivers. The gap can be attributed to contextual disparities: in Kenyan family structures, caring is frequently allocated informally among extended families, mitigating the isolated impact of time strain.

Emotional stress has modest and non-significant associations with all variables of quality-of-life (r ranging from -0.006 to 0.077), suggesting that emotional strain alone does not directly predict quality-of-life in the bivariate model. Consistent with these findings, Goto et al. (2023) determined that emotional stress alone had poor predictive capability unless it was coupled with objective burden. Applebaum and Sannes (2025) indicated that subjective distress is influenced by coping mechanisms and social support, suggesting that individuals with strong social networks and effective coping strategies may experience lower levels of distress compared to those without such resources. Conversely, Yaqoob et al. (2025) identified robust direct correlations between emotional stress and psychological quality-of-life deterioration. Sargolzaei et al. (2024) indicated that emotional exhaustion is a significant factor contributing to depression among caregivers.

Indicators of social stress (e.g., restricted friendships and diminished social engagement) have modest and non-significant correlations with quality-of-life ($r = -0.029$ to 0.086). This indicates that social disruption is not significantly correlated with an immediate drop in quality-of-life within this population. Consistent with these findings, Brown et al. (2023) discovered that social isolation does not invariably diminish quality-of-life when familial cohesion is robust. Ahmad et al. (2023) found that perceived support significantly influences social well-being, rather than the frequency of actual interactions. Acquati et al. (2023) identified significant unfavourable correlations between social isolation and quality-of-life among cancer caregivers. Similarly, Yao et al. (2024) established that social withdrawal is a strong predictor of psychological discomfort. This indicates that in the Kenyan context, extended family structures may mitigate the consequences of social isolation, hence diminishing direct relationships, which can lead to improved quality-of-life for cancer caregivers and reduce psychological discomfort.

Regression analysis indicated that these stressors, when combined, significantly predicted quality-of-life, accounting for almost 60% of its variance. The emotional burden was identified as the most significant predictor, succeeded by social and time difficulties. Consistent with this finding, Wen et al. (2025) determined that caregiver stress significantly predicts a reduction in quality-of-life across many dimensions. Likewise, Mirshahi et al. (2025) validated robust model-level predictive correlations between caregiver burden and quality-of-life (QoL). Similarly, López-Martínez et al. (2024) reported that emotional exhaustion is more influential than physical burden in predicting QoL. Social burden is the second strongest predictor ($\beta = -0.23$), indicating that reduced social engagement significantly contributes to QoL decline. Consistent with this, Cham et al. (2022) found that social isolation strongly predicts caregiver burnout. Likewise, Murayama et al. (2024) reported that reduced social support increases psychological distress.

According to the findings, physical burden significantly reduces QoL, reflecting fatigue and physical exhaustion. Consistent with this, Badger et al. (2024) found physical strain to be a major determinant of caregiver well-being. Similarly, Heravi-Karimooi et al. (2025) reported strong associations between physical exhaustion and reduced QoL. Time burden ($\beta = -0.21$) and

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developmental disruption ($\beta = -0.17$) also significantly reduce QoL, confirming that caregiver restricts personal and professional growth. Consistent with this, Xu et al. (2021) found that caregiver limits educational and occupational opportunities. Similarly, Nguyen et al. (2024) reported that time-intensive caregiver reduces QoL significantly.

6. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that caregiver stressors substantially affect the quality-of-life of family caregivers, with their impacts being predominantly synergistic rather than independent. While individual stressors exhibit weak direct correlations with quality-of-life, their cumulative effect is substantial and statistically significant, indicating that caregiver burden operates as a unified multidimensional construct. Emotional stress is the primary factor influencing the decline in quality-of-life, emphasising the critical function of psychological strain in caring results.

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